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101118217 – RE-INTEGRATE

RE-INTEGRATE

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Glossary

DoA	Description of Action
EC	European Commission
GA	Grant Agreement
SAB	Scientific Advisory Board
PC	Project Coordinator
PM	Project Manager
PMC	Project Management Committee
QAP	Quality Assurance Procedure
SC	Steering Committee
WP	Work Package
WPL	Work Package Leader

Introduction

This deliverable, details the Project Management Plan of the RE-INTEGRATE project, providing a documented plan for the management and control of the organizational, developmental, and supporting processes necessary for the successful implementation of the project.

It outlines the project overview and organizational structure, defines the responsibilities and roles of project participants, identifies the communications methods, internal and external, and specifies the general procedures and management tools that are implemented to ensure effective project management and successful project completion.

This plan will be updated and revised throughout the project to keep up with the changes, if any.

Overview of the Project

The effectiveness and ownership of scientific tools in EU and AU climate-compatible development planning has been often hindered by uncoordinated and biased model and capacity development approaches of involved actors. To address this lack of ownership, and limited uptake in policymaking, the RE-INTEGRATE initiative aims to create an inclusive environment for sharing knowledge and expertise in integrated modelling of climate compatible strategies in the AU and EU. It seeks to co-develop fit-for-purpose models at continental level and in eight AU contexts, stemming from and expanding local expertise, and to extract actionable insights for the EU and AU, while expanding modelling capacity. By fostering collaboration and addressing limitations, RE-INTEGRATE has a vision to enhance the integration of scientific insights into energy planning and policymaking processes, contributing to a sustainable and climate-resilient future.

Project Objectives

A list of project's objectives and the descriptions of these objectives can be found in the Grant Agreement (GA) Annex 1 Part B Section 1.1.

Methodology

The methodology that will be used to achieve the project's objectives can be found in the GA Annex 1 Part B Section 1.2.

Project Budget

The project's budget table can be found in the GA Annex 2.

Project Plan

The project's plan and description of work packages can be found in the GA Annex 1 Part A and B Section 3.1.

Gantt Chart

A WP-level Gantt Chart of the project can be found in the GA Annex 1 Part B Section 3.1. The detailed Gantt chart can be found in the Appendix 1.

Deliverables

Table 1 - List of Deliverables

WP.D	Name	Lead Beneficiary	Deliverable Leader	Due Date
D1.1	Project Management Plan v1	KTH	Suat Sevencan	31 Oct 2023
D1.2	Project Management Plan v2	KTH	Suat Sevencan	31 Aug 2024
D1.3	Project Management Plan v3	KTH	Suat Sevencan	31 Aug 2025
D1.4	Project Management Plan v4	KTH	Suat Sevencan	31 Aug 2026
D2.1	Workflows manual	Imperial	Carla Cannone	31 Dec 2024
D2.2	Report on Learning Quality Assessment v1	KTH	Francesco Gardumi	28 Feb 2025
D2.3	Report on Learning Quality Assessment v2	KTH	Francesco Gardumi	31 Dec 2026
D3.1	Infrastructure for enhanced 3E modelling in AU countries	E3M	Anastasis Giannousakis	31 Aug 2026
D3.2	Repository of modelling and data workflows	VTT	Juha Kiviluoma	31 Aug 2026
D3.3	Policy brief on national insights	UCT	Bruno Merven	31 Dec 2026
D4.1	Insights on regional integration	TNO	Amir Fattahi	31 Dec 2026
D5.1	Report on the gap between existing policies and model indications	UCB	Mac Cubaka	28 Feb 2026
D5.2	Final policy and investment recommendations	UCB	Mac Cubaka	28 Feb 2027
D5.3	Report on activities in T5.4 and T5.5 v1	DTU	Francesco Gardumi	28 Feb 2025
D5.4	Report on activities in T5.4 and T5.5 v2	KTH	Francesco Gardumi	28 Feb 2026
D5.5	Report on activities in T5.4 and T5.5 v3	KTH	Francesco Gardumi	28 Feb 2027
D6.1	DCE Strategy v1	ENDA	Ibra Seck Cassis	29 Feb 2024
D6.2	DCE Strategy v2	ENDA	Ibra Seck Cassis	28 Feb 2025
D6.3	DCE Strategy v3	ENDA	Ibra Seck Cassis	28 Feb 2026
D6.4	Data Management Plan V1	DTU	Xiufeng Liu	29 Feb 2024
D6.5	Data Management Plan V2	DTU	Xiufeng Liu	28 Feb 2025
D6.6	Data Management Plan V3	DTU	Xiufeng Liu	28 Feb 2026

Milestones

The list of milestones can be found in the GA Annex 1 Part A.

Project Organization

Governance Structure

Roles and Responsibilities

Descriptions of roles and responsibilities can be found in the GA Annex 1 Description of WP 1 – Project Management and Coordination.

Project Communication Strategy

In this section, we briefly describe the initial project communication strategy. This will be described in greater detail in the Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation plan. Subsequent versions of this document will refer to this plan.

Internal Communications

Below, we outline the tools and procedures to ensure clear lines of communication within the project consortium.

Project Management Tool

MS Teams will be used for project management activities, e.g., monitoring project progress, internal communications, internal reviewing and reporting, regular task updates, document repository, preparation for financial statements etc.

Internal Communications

Internal communications will be done through the project management tool.

Regular Meetings

There will be monthly WP meetings and Project Management Committee meetings. The minutes from these meetings will be stored in the document repository in Teams. WP meetings should be organised by the WP leaders. The monthly Project Management Committee meetings will be organised by the project coordinator.

Document repository

MS Teams has an embedded document repository.

Templates

Templates for reports, presentations, posters, and flyers will be made available for all the project contributors in the document repository.

External Communications and Dissemination

Dissemination Strategy

Publications

All the news or scientific journal publications produced by RE-INTEGRATE will be published open access and in compliance with the Grant Agreement. For management and protection of intellectual property in the case of co-authorship of several beneficiaries in scientific publications, the CRedit

author statement (which we'll use for all scientific publications) will pinpoint contributions. The use of data in the publications will be regulated by the Data Management Plan.

Press and Publicity

To raise RE-INTEGRATE's profile among beneficiary communities, we plan to work with influential media and organisations. These partnerships will amplify our message, raise public awareness of our initiatives and ensure greater media coverage of our actions. We will organise media events, interviews and joint campaigns to maximise the impact of our efforts.

As part of these media partnerships, we will include targeted advertising strategies to increase the visibility of our messages. This will include running ads on relevant media platforms, using paid advertising on social networks, and creating compelling advertising content. These advertising efforts will help to reach a wider audience and raise awareness of the issues surrounding energy planning, while strengthening RE-INTEGRATE's reputation within the target communities.

Website

Our website will play a central role in making publications and other relevant resources available. It will serve as an interactive platform where energy planning communities, researchers and other stakeholders can access the latest information on energy planning. Our website will include a section dedicated to educational resources, practical guides and interactive tools to facilitate the appropriation of energy planning skills.

In addition, we plan to integrate a blog into our site. This blog will serve as a central point for sharing informative articles, case studies, analyses and feedback. Our blog posts will cover a range of energy planning topics, providing in-depth and accessible information. We will also encourage participation from the online community by inviting external contributors to share their knowledge and perspectives.

The addition of a blog to our website will enrich the content, stimulate further discussion, and provide an additional resource for continuous learning about energy planning. This approach will reinforce our commitment to sharing knowledge and empowering our audiences while strengthening our online presence.

Social Media Presence

We will use social media, including X, Facebook and LinkedIn, to promote our publications, disseminate key information and encourage discussion on energy planning issues. On these platforms, we will create engaging content such as articles, informative videos, and infographics to educate our audience.

We will actively participate in relevant conversations, sharing news related to energy planning, interacting with our online community, and responding to questions and comments. In addition, we will organise virtual events, such as webinars, to engage and involve our audience.

We will monitor comments, feedback and engagement data to adjust our communication strategies in real time. This approach will allow us to maintain a dynamic presence on social media and ensure that our messages effectively reach our target audience, contributing to our goals of raising awareness and educating people about energy planning.

Communications with the European Commission (EC)

The Project Coordinator is the official interface with the RE-INTEGRATE Consortium. Therefore, all exchanges of information with the EC will be processed through the Project Coordinator or delegated through the Project Manager.

Communications to public and wider audiences

We will develop targeted awareness campaigns to inform a wider audience about the challenges of energy planning, the importance of energy sustainability, and the achievements of our RE-INTEGRATE project. These campaigns will use a variety of communication channels, including social media, online advertising and media partnerships to reach a diverse audience.

We will promote cross-sector communication by collaborating with other actors working in related fields such as the environment, sustainable development, and energy policy.

We will participate in international events and conferences to share our research and best practice. This will allow us to interact with global experts and contribute to wider discussions on energy planning challenges and solutions.

Risk Management

Strategy

The risk management strategy that is applied to the RE-INTEGRATE project to attempt to decrease the probability and impact of any events that might have negative impacts to the project outputs, schedule, or budget.

Figure 1 - Risk management process

Risk identification

A proactive/iterative approach to risk identification has been used in the RE-INTEGRATE project. Project Coordinator, Work Package Leaders, subject-matter experts and Project Manager have taken part in the risk identification process. The first iteration of this process took place during the proposal preparation, after which the risks identified were re-examined/updated during the Grant Agreement Preparation and newly identified risks were added to the list.

Risk analysis

During this phase the risks are evaluated, the type, effects of materialization, the probability and the impact level to the project of each risk are identified. The combination of probability and impact is used to evaluate the risk level and to get a list of the prioritized risks. Table 2 visualizes the Impact and Probability matrix, with risk levels marked in different colours, where the level of a risk corresponds to evaluation frequency.

Types of Risks	Probability levels	Impact levels
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Management Risk • Time Risk • Competence Risk • Technical Risk 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low • Medium • High 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Low • Medium • High

Table 2 - Probability – Impact matrix

		Impact		
		Low	Medium	High
Probability	Low	9 months	7 months	5 months
	Medium	7 months	5 months	3 months
	High	5 months	3 months	1 month

Risk response planning

The process of Risk Response Planning answers two key questions:

1. Who is responsible for the risk?
2. What should be done to mitigate the risk, i.e., decrease the probability of the risk materializing and decrease the impact of it should the risk materialise?

Strategies and plans are developed to minimize the effects of a risk to a point where the risk can be controlled and managed. For all identified risks, the various handling techniques should be evaluated in terms of feasibility, expected effectiveness, cost and schedule implications and the effect on the system's technical quality and performance. The results of the evaluation will then be documented in the risk register along with; the description of risk, effects of risk materialising, impacted WPs, risk tracker, mitigation measure and the future actions should the risk materialise.

Monitoring

Throughout the project's lifetime risks will be monitored and evaluated with the frequency selected according to the Probability – Impact Matrix. Monitoring may also provide a basis for developing additional response actions and identifying new risks and is done in a continuous manner.

During risk monitoring and control the following tasks will be performed:

- Identifying, analysing, and planning for new risks.
- Reviewing project performance information (such as progress/status reports, issues, and corrective actions).
- Re-analysing existing risks to see if the probability, impact, or mitigation measures has changed.
- Reviewing the execution of mitigation measures and analysing their effectiveness.
- Reviewing the effectiveness of the risk management strategy to determine whether changes to the approach, tools or techniques are required.

Quality Management

Quality management is fundamental to the success of the project, and the project adopts a methodology with two separated processes:

- **Quality Assurance** is the execution of processes and procedures to ensure the achievement of the objectives and to assure that the project satisfies the needs for which it was undertaken.
- **Quality Control** verifies and assesses the achievements/deliverables; it is concerned with the operational activities and techniques that are used to fulfil the requirements of quality.

Quality management is the responsibility of the PC, who defines a Quality Assurance Procedure (QAP) which ensures quality of the project management and consequently, of all deliverables and provides measurement criteria to verify the success of the project.

Quality assurance procedure

Quality assurance is the monitoring of specific project outputs to determine whether the project is performing to relevant quality standards and the identification of actions required to correct unsatisfactory performance. These quality assurance activities consist of process quality reviews followed by recommendations and possible corrective action plans.

A quality assurance procedure defines the responsibilities, templates, review processes, working methodology and quality objectives for the project. It defines internal and external processes applicable within the project, e.g., between WPs, between partners, and in some cases, between the project and external /project/body/stakeholder.

To ensure that the project outputs keep to the project's quality objective the PC will,

- make sure that all templates, standards and planning documents are available in the document repository.
- make sure that standards appropriately address the criticality of the project.
- make sure that all team members are familiar with the templates, relevant planning documents and the associated rules.
- verify that the outputs are delivered on time.
- ensure compliance with all relevant standards.
- follow the Quality Management process described in this Management Plan.

Project milestones, deliverables and the timeline are described in the DoA, GA – Annex 1. Assessing the adherence to the baseline conditions defined in the DoA is the method for evaluating the quality of both the project and its outputs.

The PC is supported by the PM in the definition of the QAP items applied to the project, and in the execution of the control activities planned or considered useful during the project. The PC also receives support, advice and help from WPLs and the EC through the Project Officer.

Document production process

During the project, many kinds of documents will be produced. It is crucial to define common formats of documents, uniform rules of their description, responsibilities, revision plans and revision procedures.

When producing any document to be distributed to at least another partner of the project, contributor will make sure that they use the template provided in the communications toolkit in the document repository and it is accessible to other contributors via the document repository.

All deliverables of the project will have the following structure:

- Cover page with general data about the document, the project logo and acknowledgement of funding (see Article 29, clause 4 in the Grant Agreement).
- History of changes table
- Table of contents
- A list of figures and a list of tables (optional, but placed here if there are any)
- A Glossary
- An Executive summary (where appropriate)
- An introduction including the scope of the document.
- Chapters constituting the body of the document.
- Possible Annexes
- All the single pages of the document will include the project name, GA number, the name of the document and the number of pages using the format “Page X of Y”

Deliverables monitoring and control.

A deliverable production process is developed for the project to ensure the quality of deliverables.

Deliverables are generated under the responsibility of the deliverable leader as indicated in Table 1, who will oversee that the deliverable is prepared in a timely manner and to the scientific quality the project desires.

Project deliverables will be held to an internal review by two people from the project but not directly involved in the deliverable. Assigned by the PC and/or PM to guarantee that it meets the objectives of the project as a whole and reflects the quality level targeted by the project. The review process is not to exceed five working days. During the review, the PC and/or PM will check the deliverable’s format and will monitor and maintain the review process.

The Deliverable leader then updates the document after the internal review, taking the reviewers’ comments into account. All the contributors to the deliverable, PC and PM should be in a copy of the internal review correspondences.

The deliverable production process, as described in Figure 3, should start eight weeks before the due date of the deliverable. The final document should be ready for editorial review a week before the due date. The deliverable leader is responsible for the scheduling of the stages of the process. The project will have a Kanban board that will have lanes for each of the steps outlined in Figure 3. Deliverable leaders are expected to update the Kanban board with the status of the deliverable as the production process progresses.

Figure 2 - Deliverable Production Process

All the deliverables of the project should adhere to the following quality aspects:

- The contribution of the deliverable to the WP and the overall goals of the project should be clearly stated.
- The objectives of the deliverable should be clearly expressed. Specifically, the deliverable should feature a short introduction paragraph that clearly states the role and duty of said document in the scope of the project.
- The deliverable's relation to previous and future deliverables in the WP and -if applicable- to deliverables from other WPs should be clearly stated.
- The relation/additions/differences to previous deliverables in the same work package (i.e. in the case the deliverable is an improved version of a previous one) should be clearly stated.
- The deliverable should be a self-contained document which can be understood without knowledge of the DoA (or previous deliverables).
- The deliverable contents should be consistent with its description in the DoA; if not, the deviation should be explained.
- The deliverable should be cohesive and concise (typically not more than 50 pages).
- The deliverable should not contain any claims that are not proven or supported by references and/or original scientific findings from RE-INTEGRATE.

In addition to the process described above, to be able to foresee potential challenges to the production of the deliverables and facilitate communicating progress on each deliverable, each WPL reports progress and challenges on the work package and on deliverable production to the SC in monthly meetings.

Change Management

The purpose of the change management is to document how the changes are managed throughout the project life cycle. It defines activities and processes related to managing changes to the project activities, deliverables, timeline, etc., as they are described in the GA.

Figure 3 - Change management process

As mentioned in the quality management section, WPLs report progress and challenges on their WPs and deliverables to the SC in monthly meetings. When a WPL identifies a challenge that might trigger a change they present it to the SC with justification. SC then assesses the change and decides whether the change should be escalated to SC. WPL then prepares the change proposal including the justification and implications of the change on cost, schedule and scope. If SC decides the change should be implemented, then the PM checks if the change triggers a GA amendment and prepares one if needed. WPL executes the change and PM verifies the change taken place and closes the change request.

Document Change Process

Any change to a document must be clearly documented in the history of changes table of the document. The reason must be clearly stated, and the significant changes should be listed with page numbers so the new text can easily be recognized.

When a change to a deliverable is requested, the deliverable leader is responsible to analyse the impact of the change to the deliverable itself as well as the overall project outcomes and may consult the PC/PM if they see fit. The deliverable leader can either approve or disapprove a change request. They then inform the originator of the request on the results of the evaluation with justification for

the decision. If the request is approved, then the deliverable leader implements the changes to the document and documents the changes in the history of changes table.

Project Reporting

Internal Reporting

WP leaders will report on work progress through the Kanban board on Teams. The PM will then collate a summarizing report to be presented in the SC meetings. Beneficiaries will report expenses through the project management tool Teams every 9 months.

Reporting to the European Commission

Project reporting to EC will be done through the Commission's Funding & Tender Opportunities portal using the System for Grant Management (SyGMA).

Appendix 1

Gantt Chart

